

GLOBAL FINANCIAL TRENDS AND THEIR IMPACT ON THE STABILITY OF THE INTERNATIONAL FINANCIAL SYSTEM

GLOBAL MOLIYAVIY TENDENSIYALAR VA ULARNING XALQARO MOLIYA TIZIMI BARQARORLIGIGA TA’SIRI

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**Annotation
Annotatsiya**

Eng - The article examines the changes in global financial markets, the processes of reforming the world financial system, and the main causes of global imbalances. In addition, attention was paid to the development of scientific conclusions and recommendations based on the study of the impact of global financial trends on the international financial system.

Uzb - Maqolada global moliya bozorlarida sodir bo‘lgan o‘zgarishlar, jahon moliya tizimini isloh qilish jarayonlari hamda global nomutanosibliklarning asosiy sabablari tadqiq etilgan. Shuningdek, global moliyaviy tendentsiyalarning xalqaro moliya tizimiga ta’sirini tadqiq etish asosida ilmiy xulosa va tavsiyalar ishlab chiqishga e’tibor qaratildi.

**Keywords:
Kalit so‘zlar:**

- ❖ *global financial system, financial architecture, capital market, balance of payments, recession, inflation, SWIFT, crypto-assets.*
- ❖ *global moliya tizimi, moliyaviy arxitektura, kapital bozori, to‘lov balansi, retsessiya, inflyatsiya, SWIFT, kripto-aktivlar.*

Introduction.

The modern global financial system is being affected by global imbalances that destabilize the development of the world economy. The negative impact of imbalances in the global financial system requires international and national regulators, monetary authorities of individual countries and their associations to develop new approaches to reforming the global financial architecture.

In the 21st century, significant changes have occurred in the global financial system that require theoretical and practical analysis. The turning point in these changes was, undoubtedly, the global economic and financial crisis of 2007-2009. After this crisis, under the influence of the processes of reforming the global financial system, serious changes

occurred both in global financial markets and in the mechanisms for their regulation. At the same time, changes began in the structure of international organizations dealing with the problems of the global financial system. In addition, this situation is further exacerbated by the new global economic crisis that began in 2020, associated with the spread of the COVID-19 pandemic, and the sharp fluctuations in the global market situation in recent years [4]. These developments have had a serious impact on many segments of the global financial system, creating instability in commodity and financial markets.

In this article, we use the term “global financial system” to refer to the global financial markets (including securities and banking markets) and the system of international institutions that regulate them in a broad sense.

The article examines the changes that have occurred in global financial markets, the processes of reforming the global financial system, and the changes in the global financial architecture designed to regulate the global financial system. Accordingly, it is intended to consider, firstly, the trends that have developed in the global financial system in the current period, and, secondly, the problems that have arisen for the global financial system as a result of fluctuations in the global financial market environment.

Literature review.

The global financial system, its conjunctural fluctuations and its impact on the economies of countries have been studied as a subject of scientific research by many economists, and these studies have important scientific approaches.

E. Zvonova, A. Kuznesov conducted scientific research on the monitoring and regulation of global financial imbalances and reform of the international financial architecture, justifying the development trends of the international financial system [7].

S.R. Moiseev and L.N. Krasavina studied the development trends and prospects of the international financial system in the context of increasing globalization of the world economy, factors affecting the stability of the international financial system, and directions for ensuring the stability of the world monetary system [9; 10].

C. Alves, J. Toporowski and M. Obstfeld developed recommendations on changes in the international financial system and their impact on the economies of countries, increasing the role of international financial organizations in ensuring the stability of the international financial system [1; 12].

C. Borio, P. Disyatat, G. Kaminsky, C. Neely studied the impact of global imbalances and financial crises on the balance of payments

of countries and the international financial system, the use of “unconventional” measures in the field of monetary policy by developed and developing countries and their impact at the international level, reforms aimed at stabilizing the international financial environment and the directions of their systematic implementation [4; 8; 11].

As is known, currently the global financial system is undergoing institutional changes under the influence of various factors. In our opinion, it is an urgent issue to identify trends inherent in the development of the international financial system, taking into account the impact of changes related to the globalization of the world economy.

Methodology.

The scientific article extensively uses induction and deduction, systematic and comparative analysis, graphical representation, and economic and statistical methods to study trends in the international financial system and the current state of fluctuations in the global financial market, changes in it, and factors affecting the global financial architecture, and to develop scientific conclusions and recommendations based on the systematization of research results.

Results and analysis.

In the short period of the 21st century (a little over 20 years), one can see various stages characteristic of the development of the global financial system. If the new century began with a crisis in the world stock market and a slowdown in the growth rates of the world economy (2000-2002), then a period characterized by the peak of the development of financial globalization began (2003-2007), which, however, gave way to the global economic and financial crisis (2007-2009), after which a period of unstable recovery of cross-border financial relations began.

Picture 1. Gross cross-border flows in leading economies (as a percentage of GDP) [15]

Gross cross-border capital flows can be used as an integral indicator reflecting the noted dynamics (see Figure 1). After the rapid growth in 2003-2007 and a sharp decline during the global economic and financial crisis, cross-border capital flows have become more volatile. However, one general trend can be noted - leading countries approached the new global economic crisis of 2020 with significantly lower values of cross-border capital flows, which is mainly due to the strengthening of protectionist tendencies in the world economy. At the same time, international capital flows in 2020 began to grow again, mainly under the influence of economic policy measures taken to overcome the crisis. In this regard, it can be noted that cross-border capital flows continue to grow in the United States and the euro area, which have continued to pursue active stimulus policies since 2021.

Since 2008, significant changes have occurred in the economic policy models of leading developed countries. In the field of monetary policy, so-called “unconventional” measures, including the policy of “quantitative easing”, have become widespread [2].

There are a number of ways to channel money into the economy during an economic crisis or recession and thereby stimulate real

growth, in which developed countries have a certain advantage. In particular, the United States is the issuer of one of the world's main reserve currencies and has the largest capital market, and the probability of a debt crisis in the country is considered very low.

At the same time, in developed countries, the main goal is not to finance budget deficits, but to support economic activity and ensure the stability of financial markets, and various non-standard approaches are widely used in this regard. This is primarily due to the limited availability of traditional monetary policy instruments in developed countries. In particular, in most of them, the difference between the Central Bank's key rates and the level of profitability of government bonds is close to zero (or negative), and Central banks use only non-traditional instruments related to the expansion of their balance sheets. In this case, quantitative and (or) qualitative easing programs are used in conjunction with fiscal policy. The demand for such instruments increases due to the limitation of the ability to transmit monetary policy decisions to the economy through the interest rate channel in conditions of interest rates close to zero.

Quantitative easing is the practice of purchasing financial assets by the Central

Bank, in which additional money is released into the economy by purchasing government bonds, corporate shares and bonds on the bank's balance sheet. As a result, the decision to ease monetary policy is transmitted to the economy through banks, and interest rates decrease (price effect).

Qualitative easing is the practice of changing the composition of assets by the Central Bank, usually by selling highly liquid assets (foreign exchange, gold, government securities, etc.) and purchasing assets with a low level of liquidity (asset-backed securities, loans from banks experiencing financial difficulties). In this case, in conditions of deep crisis, quantitative and qualitative easing programs are used together (changes in the qualitative composition of assets along with the growth of the Central Bank's balance sheet). This approach allows you to strengthen the transmission of monetary policy by directing money in circulation to specific problem areas. If during the global economic and financial crisis of 2008-2009 and after, these measures can be considered as an anti-crisis tool, then to this day we see that leading developed countries have been using them almost continuously. After the end of the "quantitative easing" policy in the United States in 2014, the European Central Bank began to actively implement asset purchase programs. During the 2020 global crisis, an increase in unconventional policy elements was observed. In the United States, the Federal Reserve System for some time assumed the functions of lending to all sectors of the economy. The experience of 2008-2022 shows that "unconventional" monetary policy measures are gradually being included in its standard tools (at least during the crisis) [3; 11]. It should be noted that the effectiveness of quantitative and qualitative easing programs in developed countries is largely controversial. In particular, money directed to the economy in many cases does not reach the real sector from the financial system and, remaining in the financial system,

causes an increase in the value of financial assets. It also creates a certain level of inflationary pressure in developed countries by increasing liquidity.

Such programs are not used in developing countries due to the insufficient development of financial and capital markets, limited aggregate supply in the economy, and persistent high inflation rates. In this case, against the background of the current deterioration of economic conditions and a reduction in aggregate supply, the injection of excess funds into the economy creates significant pressure on the inflation rate and the national currency exchange rate by increasing imports.

It should be noted that developed countries can inject large amounts of money into the economy without significant problems, which is explained by the effective establishment of commodity supply chains.

In general, the practice of injecting money into the economy, as noted above, is used in countries that do not have the opportunity to use traditional monetary policy instruments in times of crisis and where strong deflationary pressure has arisen, both to stimulate economic activity and to return inflation to the target indicator [5].

Changes in the monetary policies of leading developed countries have affected the dynamics of global liquidity. In this case, the concept of global liquidity in a narrow sense refers to credit instruments (bank loans and debt securities) in the relevant currency that are in circulation outside national jurisdictions.

Since 2000, despite the fluctuations in cross-border capital flows that we noted above, global liquidity in the US dollar has been steadily growing. Of course, the unconventional monetary policy pursued by the Federal Reserve System in 2008-2014 and 2020-2021 was an important factor in ensuring global liquidity.

The growth of global liquidity in the euro, which until 2007 ran almost in parallel with dollar liquidity, stagnated in 2009-2016, and

only then did its growth resume at a pace that lagged behind the growth of dollar liquidity.

Picture 2. Global liquidity outside national jurisdictions (end of period, trillions of US dollars) [16]

It was during this period, as noted above, that the European Central Bank actively implemented asset purchase programs. Finally, after a short-term increase in 2007-2012, liquidity in the Japanese yen began to decline sharply in 2015, at the level of 0.4-0.5 trillion

US dollars. The comparative dynamics of global liquidity in various leading currencies shows that the US dollar has strengthened its position in the global monetary system in the period following the global financial and economic crisis of 2007-2009.

Picture 3. Government spending in developed countries (as a percentage of GDP) [15]

In the area of fiscal policy, qualitative changes are more difficult to identify, but quantitative changes are certainly present: a significant increase in public spending (Figure 3) and public debt was observed during the period under review. Two periods of significant

growth in public spending relative to GDP are clearly visible: 2009 and 2020. Moreover, the second period is characterized by a significant increase in spending, which, despite a slight decrease in 2021, remains at record levels in the 21st century (with the exception of Sweden,

where public spending has been consistently high).

The increase in public spending has led to an increase in the level of public debt. Gross public debt in the group of developed countries has grown from 70 percent of GDP at the beginning of the 21st century to 120 percent of GDP in 2021.

It is worth noting that the processes of increasing debt burden have had a significant impact on the activities of the public sector. In the modern world economy, the debt burden has increased significantly, even approaching critical levels. Since 2010, after the global

economic and financial crisis, the debt burden has been on the rise, mainly through the public sector and, to a lesser extent, non-financial corporations. The scale of the problem can be assessed based on the fact that, according to the calculations of the Institute of International Finance, in 2020 the volume of global debt amounted to 360 percent of world GDP, although in 2021 it decreased slightly (to 351 percent), but still remains at a high level.

In general, throughout the 21st century, significant fluctuations in volatility in global financial markets can be observed.

Picture 4. VIX (Volatility index) index values from 2000 to 2024 [17]

The continuation of volatility in the world stock market was observed at the beginning of the 21st century due to crisis events, but the volatility indicator recorded its highest peak during the two global economic crises of the current century, in October-November 2008 and March 2020. After 2020, the index values were subject to significant fluctuations. It is noteworthy that during the period of increasing globalization trends, especially in 2003-2007, a decrease in volatility was observed in the world stock market. Over the past few years, the stock market has repeatedly faced the risk of “bursting” the “bubble” formed after the global economic and financial crisis of 2007-2009: including in 2018, during the global crisis of

2020, and during the period of increased geopolitical tensions in late 2021 - early 2022.

The development of the global financial system is also characterized by the intensification of monopolization processes at the cross-border level, especially in the infrastructure sector.

A striking example in the banking services market is SWIFT, the threat of disruption from which is considered one of the most severe forms of financial sanctions. At the same time, monopolization processes have also developed in other sectors, for example, in the securities market, where exchanges have actively carried out cross-border mergers and formed alliances. As a result, under the influence of marketization, internationalization

and digitalization processes in the world stock market, several cross-border exchange holdings have been formed, such as Intercontinental Exchange, NASDAQ OMX Group, Deutsche Börse Group, London Stock Exchange, which manage securities trading and post-trade services. In particular, clearing services at the cross-border level are mainly controlled by two organizations (Euroclear and Clearstream).

During the period under review, the issue of global imbalances was periodically actively discussed at the international level. According to statistical data, the scale of this problem can be assessed by the degree of deviation of the

current account balance of payments in various leading countries and regions of the world economy from zero. In particular, in 2023, a negative current account balance was recorded in developing countries on the European continent and countries such as the United Kingdom, Canada, and Australia. In countries such as Indonesia, Malaysia, the Philippines, Singapore, and Thailand, where the economies of Asia are developing rapidly, positive trends in the current account balance of payments have been maintained for years. In the countries of Southern Africa, in recent years, an increase in the negative balance of payments can be seen.

Table 1

Changes in the current account balance of the balance of payments (in billions of US dollars)
[15]

Country/region name	2008	2017	2018	2019	2020	2021	2022	2023
EU	-119,7	482,8	490,2	469,6	410,7	634,4	178,2	431,5
China	420,6	188,7	24,1	102,9	248,8	352,9	401,9	271,4
Middle East and Central Asia	348,4	-38,2	111,4	15,6	-116,0	132,0	406,8	194,6
Latin America and the Caribbean	-43,7	-99,1	-146,1	-112,8	-15,8	-102,9	-142,3	-115,3
ASEAN-5	69,8	96,8	56,2	78,6	99,5	77,8	82,6	76,7
Southern African countries	3,0	-33,7	-38,1	-55,8	-45,5	-18,4	-38,7	-53,3
Developing countries in Europe	-57,8	-25,0	62,7	49,4	2,0	66,5	123,1	-20,7
UK, Canada, Australia	-166,0	-178,5	-189,4	-109,7	-91,8	-3,4	-104,8	-132,5
USA	-696,5	-367,6	-439,8	-441,8	-597,1	-831,4	-971,6	-795,2
Japan	142,6	203,5	177,8	176,3	149,9	196,8	90,6	141,2

The most acute problem of global imbalances was in the period before the global economic and financial crisis, peaking in 2008, and then the crisis itself reduced the severity of the problem. The causes of global imbalances can be interpreted in different ways. Developed countries have accused developing countries of regulating exchange rates and creating this problem, while developing countries, on the contrary, have accused developed countries of pursuing excessive stimulus policies [13].

Researchers at the Bank for International Settlements have recognized that current account imbalances are the reverse side of what is happening in the world of financial flows,

and therefore it is more appropriate to look at gross capital flows rather than the current account balance. In this regard, it is worth paying attention to the growth of global imbalances in 2021, when their scale began to approach the level reached before the crisis of 2007-2009.

The impact of the widespread digitalization processes of recent years on the global financial system will be long-lasting. Here, two main areas of influence can be distinguished: 1) competition between traditional and new forms of financial intermediation and 2) the emergence and

spread of private digital currencies and crypto-assets.

Bigtex companies, which initially specialized in the non-financial sector, are actively entering the financial services markets (payments, lending, insurance, etc.). Here they compete with more strictly regulated traditional financial institutions. Accordingly, the problem of regulatory arbitrage arises. As a result, risks to financial stability may arise due to increased concentration, accumulation of excessive debt, operational risks, etc. [14].

Since the fall of 2020, there has been a significant increase in the market capitalization of private digital currencies (cryptocurrencies and stablecoins), which is mainly explained by the increase in the value of Bitcoin. In the fall of 2021, the capitalization of this market exceeded \$ 2.5 trillion. Such an increase in private digital currencies has accelerated the activity of central banks in creating their own digital currencies. As a result of the development of the global financial system, an imbalance arises between the global activity of global financial and currency markets and the national level of their regulation. The processes of reforming the global financial system, which began during the global financial and economic crisis of

2007-2009 and continued after its end, were aimed at helping to eliminate this imbalance [7]. However, the reform mainly concerned the global banking system and the over-the-counter derivatives market, and a number of segments were less affected by increased regulation (primarily the securities market, as well as the emerging field of digital finance). As a result, global regulatory arbitrage has emerged between different segments of the global financial system, which has led to the accumulation of risks in less regulated sectors. Finally, it should be noted that during the period under review, the balance of power between two different groups of countries has changed significantly - developed countries and developing countries, on the one hand, and emerging market economies, on the other. Data calculated on the basis of the share of world GDP measured at current exchange rates indicate a steady strengthening of the position of emerging market economies and developing countries in the world economy during 2007-2013. Then the ratio of developed countries to countries in this group stabilized at 60:40, but after the global economic crisis of 2020, the share of emerging market economies and developing countries began to grow again.

Picture 4. Share of different groups of countries in world GDP (at current exchange rates, in percent) [15]

Meanwhile, there have been no fundamental changes in the global regulatory system, in which developed countries continue

to play a leading role. Although the process of reforming the global financial system is under the auspices of the G20 group, the agenda is

still set by developed countries. Despite the partial revision of the quota system in the traditional institutions of the global monetary and financial architecture, such as the International Monetary Fund and the World Bank Group, leading developed countries continue to control the decision-making process.

Now let us consider the main trends that have emerged in the development of the world economy and the global financial system over the past two years.

As a result of disruptions in the supply chains of energy resources and food supplies, including under the influence of sanctions imposed on certain countries by leading developed countries and their allies, prices on world commodity markets have sharply increased. As a result, the global inflation problem, which began in 2020-2021 with the extremely loose monetary and fiscal policies pursued by leading developed countries, has intensified. According to the IMF, in the first quarter of 2022, the annual inflation rate in the United States was 8 percent, and in the euro area it was 6.1 percent.

As a result, the central banks of developed countries faced a difficult dilemma: on the one hand, it was necessary to support the post-crisis recovery, and on the other hand, the severity of the inflation problem required urgent intervention. As a result, the US Federal Reserve began the process of normalizing monetary policy.

An increase in interest rates by central banks leads to an overall increase in interest rates in the economy, which, especially in the medium and long term, exacerbates the debt problem. However, for countries with emerging market economies and developing countries, the aggravation of the debt problem may already be of a short-term nature, as evidenced by the events in Sri Lanka. The process of monetary policy normalization in the leading developed countries has exacerbated the situation for this group of countries, which

has led to capital outflows [6]. In addition, energy and food importers are suffering the most from the acceleration of global inflation. As a result, the "damage" situations among emerging market economies, which were observed in the early 1990s and 2000s, may recur. As limited financial resources are increasingly directed to solving economic and military-political security problems, a number of long-term tasks that the global financial system is designed to solve (in particular, climate change and the fight against inequality) are currently at risk.

Conclusion and suggestions.

One of the main reasons for the sharp changes in the global financial system in recent years is the process of financial globalization. This process is characterized by cyclical fluctuations in the global financial system and international financial markets, international capital migration, the introduction of innovative methods of organizing and managing currency transactions.

In general, based on the above data, we can see an increase in instability in the global financial system. This situation is directly related to the macroeconomic changes taking place in the world, increasing international competition, fluctuations in international financial markets, the expansion of financial and economic restrictions, and high inflationary expectations. It is difficult to predict the next changes that may occur in the international financial system from an economic point of view, since the changes that have occurred in the global financial architecture in recent years and the factors that have influenced it are playing an increasingly important role.

In the current rapidly developing economy, reforming the international financial system is an inevitable trend in its development. To form a stable financial system, it is necessary to create a solid international trade and economic environment, regulate

capital movements, and coordinate the activities of international financial institutions. In this process, it is advisable to increase resilience to external risks and expand the ability to resolve financial crises.

Within the framework of financial globalization, the following conditions can be distinguished that affect the development of the international financial system:

- creating an effective system of international financial supervision and regulation with a clear distribution of powers and responsibilities;
- carrying out reforms at the global level to ensure the balanced and sustainable

development of the international financial system;

- improving the mechanisms of multilateral negotiations and international agreements to reduce global socio-economic tensions and reduce the scope of application of financial sanctions;
- introducing effective measures aimed at protecting against international financial risks and adverse changes in world markets;
- reducing the risk of financial crises and the scale of their impact on the economies of countries;
- developing measures aimed at reducing investors' financial losses under the influence of possible future crisis processes.

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